

2D Spectroscopy Helps Visualize the Influence of Spectral Motion on Chromophore Response

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Understanding the effect of spectral motion on the electronic couplings in multi-chromophore systems is a challenging task. In this issue of *Chem*, Rolczynski et al. introduce two methods of analyzing and visualizing correlations between electronically coupled chromophores and their local vibrational structure by employing two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy on a photosynthetic pigment-protein complex.

Pigment-protein antenna complexes employed by photosynthetic organisms spearhead the conversion of sunlight into chemicals. Although the spectrum of sunlight captured by light-harvesting complexes is decided primarily by the type of chromophores bound to the protein, the protein scaffold itself finetunes the energy funnel by controlling electronic couplings and tweaking the spectrum of each chromophore.¹ Two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy (2DES) has made it possible to test the conventional model for predicting the energy-transfer rate, given that it provides direct access to the couplings among electronic states and information about correlations between spectra.² By measuring the third-order polarization of a system, this Fourierbased technique provides access to both population and coherence dynamics. Whereas population relaxation results in the exponential growth and decay of spectral features—energytransfer dynamics—coherence produced by short-laser-pulse excitation results in oscillations in peak amplitudes. Many 2DES experiments on pigment-protein complexes have detected coherent oscillations—sometimes lasting hundreds of femtoseconds (a timescale well beyond that expected for electronic dephasing in these “wet and noisy” systems)—on the crosspeaks of 2DES maps.^{3,4} These observations have generated an intense scientific debate, pushing research toward a quantum mechanical picture to better explain such unexpected results. In this issue of *Chem*, Rolczynski et al. provide new methodologies for the analysis of 2DES experimental data in order to explain the long-lasting oscillatory behavior in the pigment-protein complex known as the Fenna-Matthews-Olson (FMO) protein.⁵ This complex transmits the energy from the light-harvesting chlorosome aggregate to the reaction center in the photosynthetic units of a green sulfur bacterium.⁶ The FMO complex has recently become a widely studied photosynthetic antennae. The crystal structure of the protein pigment complex (known to atomic resolution) reveals that the FMO contains a small number of chromophores, making this complex a manageable system for theoretical simulations of energy transfer. Specifically, seven bacteriochlorophyll (Bchl) a chromophores are electronically coupled (in most samples studied), forming seven excitons. The asymmetric arrangement of the chromophores inside the protein results in distinct and optically allowed electronic transitions that fall within the typical bandwidth of an ultrafast pulse produced by a Ti-sapphire laser. These properties make the FMO an ideal system for studying energy transfer with 2DES. Reports of long-lasting oscillatory beating in the 2DES experiment on the FMO complex have been initially interpreted as superpositions of excitonic states formed from electronically coupled BChls. Recently it has been suggested instead that coherent oscillations can originate from (1) pure vibrational states,⁷ (2) vibronic (a combination of coupled electronic and vibrational) states,⁸ or (3) pure electronic states experiencing correlated nuclear motions.⁹ Thus, the influence of the vibrational structure on the electronic coherence and decoherence in pigment-protein complexes still needs more systematic experimental investigation. The report in this issue of

Chem offers a new approach to observing the properties of the coherent signals in photosynthetic systems. Rolczynski et al. employed two methods of extracting information from the third-order nonlinear response of the system on the basis of spectrograms that correlate the energy associated with specific excitons with their vibrational motions through a “sliding-window” time-domain analysis. Specifically, 2D-STEPS (two-dimensional single-time-domain exciton perturbation spectroscopy) revealed that synchronized excited-state vibrations remained in phase for each exciton over a picosecond, suggesting that the electronic coherence among excitons might be prolonged as a result of synchronized nuclear motion. 2D-STEPS maps provide clear data visualization of how the nuclear motion modulates the electronic state of each exciton and how the excitons show synchronized spectral motion after excitation. The second approach, 2D-TRIPS (two-dimensional time-resolved interexciton perturbation spectroscopy), probes how the nuclear motion localized on a specific exciton can affect another one. 2D-TRIPS, although less intuitive, revealed that couplings do exist between the nuclear motion of distinct excitons, similarly to coupling between numerous harmonic oscillators. In particular, 2D-TRIPS maps show that nuclear motions localized on a specific exciton do affect the energy gap of other excitons in a correlated manner, such that energy levels do not fluctuate randomly. Further elucidation of how these collective nuclear motions influence coupled multi-chromophore systems could help us understand how energy-transfer dynamics can be optimized and perhaps directed.

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